

Alamathala: An augmented reality comic of the Philippine mythology for the students of St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

The study aims to develop an augmented reality comic that will help in immersing the students to the AR technology. The study also aims to promote cultural awareness to younger generations as the concept of the comic revolves around the Philippine mythology. The researchers used quantitative research design in order to interpret the numerical data in determining the output's performance and the evaluation of the students. The ALAMATHALA augmented reality comic has been proven to help in immersing the students in the technology as all the features of the ALAMATHALA augmented reality comic has achieved exceedingly well results and overall evaluation of the comic output has been satisfactorily resolved, thus the researchers are able to successfully develop an augmented reality comic that meets and exceeds high standards.

Keywords: Augmented reality, comic, digital art, Philippine lore, Philippine mythology.

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Introduction

A comic (Filipino: *Komiks*) is a form of literature that lets the reader envision and relate to what the artist is expressing from one panel to another. It was popularized by the United States and the United Kingdom during the 1930s. Philippine comics are somewhat mirror images of popular American comics; a lot of readers can relate to the concepts and cultures that are being expressed by the artist (McCloud, 1994). Although the popularity of local Filipino comics is declining, some of the local authors are still fighting to have their works published; making concepts, designs and iconic characters that would entice the Filipino readers (Gutierrez, 2014).

Other forms of entertainment over-shadow comic books. Some production companies adapt comics into animations or films; commonly featuring folklore and mythologies from Egyptians, Greeks, or the Norse. Filipinos have their own mythology that are sometimes featured in TV shows, movies and news outlets. Historically, pre-colonial Filipinos passed down stories from generation to generation. These stories were populated with often-impossible circumstances and creatures beyond mundane imagination. Most of these tales depict warnings; telling a person not to mess with these creatures or to offer penance for mistakes made. This tradition of orally passing down stories is still practiced at present by the country's indigenous groups, but not so much by the common Filipino (Byrne, 2014).

Philippine folklore has an array of stories varying from myths, tales, fables, superstition, epics, and legends. These stories come from the vast lore that spans the lands of Luzon, Visayas

and Mindanao. Often in those stories, various creatures lurk in the deep blue or the misty lands, some of which may have various powers, abilities or mystical items (Clark, 2016).

The rapid growth of technology harbored new innovations in experiencing the way people consume media. More time and resources are spent to further push the boundaries of creating, developing and harnessing the idea of viewing interactive media. Broadly speaking, folklore is a culture's spiritual, verbal, and material aspects that have been passed on verbally, by imitation, or by documentation. Often, language, ethnicity, age, profession, and/or locality are shared by people with the same culture (Eslit, 2012). This is a material traditionally passed down from a generation to another, often through word of mouth, in order to be preserved. Within the Spanish occupation of the Philippines for three centuries, records of the local's beliefs and practices had been successfully eliminated. Despite this, a lot of early Filipino beliefs survived as "superstitions."

At the beginning of every artwork is an idea. Stimulated with ample emotion and a zealous artistic drive, an idea can be formed into art. Art is a vast subject with a wide range of mediums for one to use. One of the later methods, and most frequently used to this date, is digital.

Comics, along with Filipino mythology, have gone down in popularity within the Philippines; plain comics lack luster, and some might even call it stale. There are many ways of implementing with the usage of smartphones and other devices that can create the illusion of moving images from the virtual world; this is called Augmented Reality (Bran et al., 2020). Augmented Reality (AR) is basically connecting a virtual image to real-world objects using barcodes or Quick Response (QR) codes. With the use of AR, virtual images over a comic book create the illusion of moving images, this allows readers to visualize and engage with what the artist is trying to convey more easily (Lambie, 2015; Mercieca, 2016).

To execute the Augmented Reality technology, the researchers used the concept of Philippine mythology in the story. Digital art and animation were used to add motions for the comic illustration. With AR, comic pages come to life, add even more layers to the experience, and remove the limitations of static imagery that even the greatest artists are bound by (Hashim et al., 2018; Wershler & Sinervo, 2017). AR not only adds more details written in the book, but also crosses entire segments out and changes what the reader sees. With the two combined, it gives the readers a gateway into a brilliantly realized world with a strongly told story and beautiful art (Portalés, 2018).

Though there are many advantages, there are also things to be considered from budget to skills. An artist should invest on workshops and trainings (from hardcore coding for image recognition and animation mapping) to learn how the AR would work on a specific comic. Though they can ask for help from a specialist, the requirements of such a project are expensive for it to become successful. A good storyline and concept must be considered before adding such elements so that it would become more appealing to the readers. All the information gathered would exponentially help the researchers bridge the gap between AR and comics as storytelling mediums. This would unlock a new level of immersion and storytelling that would bring new ways of telling a visual narrative and can better communicate a compelling narrative experience (Chalimov, 2020; De Vera & Arong, 2018). The study would help create AR as a storytelling tool for the local comic industry and bring relevance for its potential to produce new ideas, concepts, and stories to the Filipino comic book landscape.

The purpose of the research study is to create a Filipino comic revolving on the topic of Philippine folklore and mythologies, with the use of Augmented Reality (AR) in order to help

immerse the younger generation about the Philippine mythology. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the features of the AR comic that will help in the enhancement of delivering information about the Philippine mythology to the students?
2. What are the respondents' evaluation of the AR comic, in terms of?
 - 2.1. Aesthetic
 - 2.2. Content;
 - 2.3. Quality; and
 - 2.4. Augmented Reality Technology?
3. How will the Augmented Reality Technology help immerse the younger generations to promote, disseminate, support, and further develop Augmented Reality creations?

Methodology

The researchers used quantitative research design to interpret the numerical data in determining the output's performance and the evaluation of the students. This research makes use of a descriptive and evaluative research design to illustrate the concepts and ideas for the comic development. The proponents aimed to present and assess the performance of the augmented reality comic to the readers. The total respondents of the study are one-hundred fifty (150) students of St. Dominic College of Asia composing of fifty (50) senior high school students and one hundred (100) college students.

The researchers utilized questionnaires as one of their instruments. The questionnaire was designed to obtain the necessary information from responses and suggestions made by the respondents. This tool was prepared by the researchers and was developed by reading reference materials. Included in the questionnaire is the rating of the quality of the prototype or output as seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Rating scale criteria

Rating	Remarks
4.51 – 5.00	Excellent
3.51 – 4.50	Very Good
2.51 – 3.50	Good
1.51 – 2.50	Poor
1.00 – 1.50	Needs Improvement

The proponents conducted a survey for the primary data collection. The handling of questionnaires was done personally and through online forms. A demonstration of the comic output is required before proceeding to survey the respondents. Instructions in installing and using the given application are stated in the online form. The researchers also facilitated the demonstration of the output and the retrieval of the questionnaires. To interpret the data effectively, weighted mean is used to assess the effectiveness of a specific augmented reality comic.

Multimedia Design and Development

Initiation Phase

In the initiation phase, the researchers developed the elements needed for the pre-production stage. Considering modern trends to improve and make the comic more engaging, the proponents determined the use of augmented reality. This phase involved brainstorming and research to develop the plot, theme, and character backstories. The proponents decided to focus the theme of the story on Philippine mythology, as the study intends to promote Philippine cultural awareness. Following the prototype evaluation, the development of the plot and characters was revised and implemented.

Specification Phase

The technical feasibility is analyzed in the specification phase. The proponents carried out trials for augmented reality programs that will best suit their desired look of the output. The creation process required a desktop computer program that is partnered with a mobile device with camera access. The users can view the output through the required specifications using the Artivive Application. The application also requires an internet connection to recognize the illustration and load the animation. The hardware requirements include an Android or iOS mobile device with a camera.

The first augmented reality application used for making the comic interactive was the EyeJack Augmented Reality Application. The illustrations and animations were uploaded in the EyeJack Desktop Creator which runs in computer operating MacOS. The published work is only available on mobile devices running iOS, an operation exclusively for Apple Devices.

A fee is required for the project to be published on platforms running an Android operating system. The application requires the EyeJack mobile application to be installed on a mobile device with a camera access and an internet connection. Each illustration will have a designated unique QR Code to be scanned to load the animation in this application.

After the testing of the output prototype, the researchers had opted for a different Augmented Reality Software which is Artivive. The illustrations and animations were uploaded and published in the Artivive Bridge Creator website. The Artivive Augmented Reality application can only support three (3) free projects per registered account to be published, and a fee will be required for additional projects.

The published project can be launched in the Artivive mobile application which runs in mobile devices operating both Android and iOS systems. The application needs the mobile application to be installed on mobile devices with camera access and an internet connection throughout the whole experience.

Design Phase

In the design phase, the researchers determined the desired look of the comic. This phase involves finalizing the plot, character designs and turnarounds, storyboards, and layout of the

output. Revisions and improvements of the elements are followed based on the prototype evaluation.

Figure 1. Alamathala comic book cover

Figure 2. Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao character concepts

Production Phase

The research problem resulted in multiple ways of creating a compilation of traditional comics and augmented reality. Knowing that design problems would be present, such as stylistic choices, as the researchers had decided to create original renditions of the chosen Philippine folklore. The technicality present in the output was established by the proponents of the research with the aspiration of immersion and interaction. Therefore, the researchers sought ways to bring the illustrations and pages to life (Cahill, 2016).

The main elements of the comic are developed in the production phase. Illustrations are digitally created following the prepared designs and storyboards. In the production of physical

copy of the comic, the illustrations of each pages are printed and bound. The planned sequences are digitally animated, rendered, and calibrated in their designated illustrations. The illustration and animation are uploaded and published in the augmented reality desktop application.

Review and Evaluation Phase

The pilot testing of the prototype is profoundly important in the enhancement of the comic output. Revisions and improvements in designs and storylines were suggested. Changes in technical aspects were also made. A notable restriction in the EyeJack augmented reality application during the time of conducting the research was the application being limited to mobile devices running iOS. The researchers sought an alternative application that will be suitable for the comic output and more viable in different platforms because it was reviewed that the seclusion made the study inaccessible for consumption of a broader audience. Thus, the researchers had settled for the alternative, the Artivive Augmented Reality Application. In the review and evaluation phase, the output was examined and revised recurrently to achieve the desired outcome as the research study applied developments and refinements suggested from previous reviews. The evaluation of the final output has resulted in overwhelmingly positive reviews.

Delivery and Implementation Phase

In the delivery and implementation phase, the research addresses the level of client support, performance support, and ongoing maintenance. Through the initial surveys that had been made and collected, the feedback shows that the output was found entertaining and highly favored by the respondents. The positive reception has had an impact for the consideration of publishing the Alamathala comic and more related works that can uncover the possibilities of augmented reality and traditional comics.

With the nature of the output, it is required to maintain continuous support of the output made through online and offline backups. The digital files are stored and backed up by the researchers. However, the file linking process to the augmented reality application relies heavily on the Artivive Bridge Website, thus preparations will be made for future applications and updates to the accounts tied with the Alamathala property.

Results and Discussion

To assess the output provided, individuals were surveyed about its contents according to the following criteria: Aesthetic, Quality, Content, and Augmented Reality. The set criteria were essential in weighing the audience satisfaction from the output exhibited.

The features of the Augmented Reality Comic that will help in the enhancement of information delivery about Philippine mythology to students

Table 2. Comic book overall rating

Criteria	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Aesthetics – visual appeal to the audience	4.82	Excellent
Quality – output has met or exceeded standard quality	4.72	Excellent
Content – effectiveness of the concept	4.61	Excellent
AR Technology – effectiveness of engagement	4.69	Excellent
Overall	4.71	Excellent

From the survey results gathered from the questionnaires given to the respondents, the researchers found out that the comic’s visual aspect or aesthetics of the comics, by determining the comic’s visual appeal to the audience, has significantly helped in enhancing the learning experience for the audience. It received the highest percentage out of the overall criteria with a weighted mean of 4.82. It was followed by quality, in determining whether the output has met or exceeded standard quality with a weighted mean of 4.72. The last two criteria of content (effectiveness of the idea and concept) and the AR technology (availability of the technology and effectiveness in engaging the audience) were given 4.61 and 4.69, respectively. With the overall weighted mean of 4.71, the respondents’ assessment of each feature of the Alamathala comic book resulted in overwhelmingly positive reviews.

The respondents’ evaluation of the AR comic in terms of Aesthetics, Content, Quality, and Augmented Reality Technology

Aesthetics

Table 3. Comic book aesthetics overall rating

Criteria	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Art Style – uniqueness in portraying the subject	4.81	Excellent
Color Palette – efficacy of using a range of colors in creation	4.80	Excellent
Creativity – illustration with the use of original ideas	4.83	Excellent
Overall	4.82	Excellent

The respondents assessed the aesthetic appeal of the Alamathala comic book as Excellent with a weighted mean in Art Style: 4.81, Color Palette: 4.80, Creativity: 4.83, and an overall rating of 4.82. The art styles used in the comic book had the highest mark in the aesthetics and overall criteria, proving the output appeals to the eyes of the readers.

Quality

Table 4. Comic book quality overall rating

Criteria	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Organization – efficient and orderly approach in illustrating concepts and ideas	4.64	Excellent
Design – arrangement and execution of an idea	4.79	Excellent
Cleanliness – consistency in keeping the design from being convoluted	4.69	Excellent
Overall	4.72	Excellent

The respondents assessed the quality of the Alamathala comic book as Excellent with a weighted mean in Organization: 4.64, Design: 4.79, Cleanliness: 4.69, and an overall rating of 4.72. In quality, the comic book design received the highest rate, showing that the arrangement and execution of ideas were presented well.

Content

Table 5. Comic book content overall rating

Criteria	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Information – providing interesting and/or useful information	4.62	Excellent
Composition – organization of the elements	4.60	Excellent
Language – effectiveness of the usage of Filipino (Tagalog) language	4.59	Excellent
Overall	4.61	Excellent

The respondents assessed the content of the Alamathala comic book as Excellent with a weighted mean in Information: 4.62, Composition: 4.60, Language: 4.59, and an overall rating of 4.61. The results showed that the output has provided enough content emphasizing Philippine mythology — therefore sparking the interest of the readers.

Augmented Reality

Table 6. Comic book content overall rating

Criteria	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Ease of Operation – degree of simplicity to which the application intends to operate	4.68	Excellent
User-Friendliness – the application is easy to use and not difficult to understand	4.70	Excellent
Immersion – effectiveness in actively engaging and captivating the viewer	4.73	Excellent
Overall	4.69	Excellent

The respondents assessed the augmented reality feature of the Alamathala comic book as Excellent with a weighted mean in Ease of Operation: 4.68, User-Friendliness: 4.70, Immersion: 4.73, and an overall rating of 4.69. Given the highest mark on immersion, the results proved that the comic book with an augmented reality feature has delighted the readers, engaging their interest further.

The help of Augmented Reality Technology in immersing the younger generations to promote, disseminate, support, and further develop Augmented Reality Creations

Table 7. Comic book AR technology – Immersive Criterion

Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Senior High School	4.67	Excellent
College	4.75	Excellent
Overall	4.69	Excellent

The immersive criterion for the Alamathala comic book in terms of AR technology aspect was greatly assessed and divided into two classifications. The Senior High School category was interpreted as Excellent with a weighted mean of 4.67, while the College category was interpreted as Excellent with a weighted mean of 4.75 and an overall weighted mean of 4.73, interpreted as Excellent.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study assessed the features of the augmented reality comic that will help in the enhancement of information delivery about Philippine mythology to the students. The respondents' review of the output contents resulted in the highest rating under the informative criteria; therefore, the output produced is proven to be beneficial in terms of providing information about the Filipino mythological stories. The visual aspect or aesthetics of the comic, gaining the highest rate in the overall criteria, has greatly influenced the enhancement of the learning experience of the readers.

During the respondents' evaluation of the AR comic, in terms of aesthetics, content, quality, and augmented reality technology, the survey has conducted an outstanding result of 4.73. Following the respondents' evaluation, in accordance to the information based on the aesthetic, quality, content, and augmented reality, the Alamathala comic book were all reviewed with "Excellent" remarks. This proves that the output produced is both beneficial and satisfying to the readers in terms of being informed or reformed of Filipino mythological stories, whilst also being aesthetically pleased and immersed with the augmented reality comic.

The augmented reality technology also helped to immerse the younger generations to promote, disseminate, support, and further develop augmented reality creations. The engagement of students to the output and the showcasing of the technology has helped in influencing the students about learning and developing augmented reality comics as the evaluation of the augmented reality technology resulted in the highest rating in the immersive criteria.

The comic output can be further developed by exploring different topics or concepts to be produced and applied as a learning instrument for educators to make lessons more engaging to the students. The virtual elements of the augmented reality comic should be improved such as adding refined animations, narrations or voice-overs, and translations, to further enhance the user's experience. As technology is improving and continuing to advance, the research concept is time relevant and can serve as a starting point in the enhancement and development of other augmented reality products in the future.

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